

EIC COMMUNITIES

D1.7 Knowledge base on how to build and promote sustainable and inclusive communities around EIC portfolios

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- * PU = Public
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1. Introduction

1.1 List of abbreviations

ADHD – Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder

BIPOC - Black people, Indigenous people and People of Colour

CoP – Community of Practice

EIC – European Innovation Council

EIC PMs – Programme Managers

EIL– English as an international language

EIT – European Institute of Innovation and Technology

ENL – English as Native Language

EU – European Union

LGBTQIA+ – lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer, questioning, intersex, asexual, and the + holds space for the expanding and new understanding of different parts of the very diverse gender and sexual identities.

RHC – Renewable Heating and Cooling

SDGs – United Nation’s Sustainable Development Goals

WLP – Woman Leadership Programme

WP – Work Package

BSOs – Business Support Organisations

IHUBs – Innovation Hubs

1.2. Project Overview

The following report should serve as guide on how to promote inclusive communication and community building under the scope of the “**EIC Communities: Building Synergies and Communities around EIC Portfolios to raise the impact of the EIC deep tech research**” project, henceforth mentioned as EIC Communities.

The EIC Communities project seeks to improve the visibility and impact of the EIC portfolios, through the creation of three thematic Communities of Practice (CoPs): Cleantech, Industry and Health. These CoPs, which will include a pre-selected number of EIC projects and stakeholders under the relevant vertical, will foster interactions and synergies on an intra and cross-community level.

What is an EIC Portfolio

EIC Portfolios are sets of actions developed around clusters of projects with thematic similarities or contributing to the same EIC Challenge. EIC awarded projects can be a part of one or several thematic or challenge-based portfolios, to benefit from a productive setting through which to advance their solutions.

The portfolio activities are identified and developed by the EIC Programme Managers. Throughout this process, they consult with the EIC innovators under the portfolio in question, with the relevant Commission services and, when appropriate, with other interested parties that can have a stake or interest in the activities. Examples of activities include conferences, workshops, meetings, experience and data sharing, as well as participation in any relevant EIC Business Acceleration Services.

The goal of the EIC Portfolios is to stimulate internal cooperation to achieve objectives, enhance research, innovation and business opportunities, as well as advance understanding and improvement of regulatory framework and, finally, strengthening the EIC Community.

Source: [European Innovation Council Work Programme, 2024](#)

The activities organised to nurture these collaborations will include pitching sessions, matchmaking between projects, Portfolio Days and online interactive academies, thematic workshops and the re-launch of the Future Tech Week. The outcome and lessons learned from the activities should help EIC Programme Managers (EIC PMs) design future community models and promote engagement practices to further stimulate the creation of networks around EIC Portfolios.

The final step to maximise the impact of the activities will be the creation of communication materials which will promote the benefits of being a part of the EIC Portfolio's ecosystem, and advocate for the added value provided to its current and potential members. Impactful, strategic communication will help engage the CoP members, but also draw in innovators and experts from a broader audience.

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1.3 Objectives of the Report

The European Union and its institutions are committed to the United Nation’s Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), including promoting gender equality and establishing inclusive institutions at all levels (*Transforming our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, 2015*). The CoPs created under the project must reflect and support these efforts. The “EIC Communities” project can play a role in the enforcement of SDGs 5, 16 and 17, which concern gender equality, institutional inclusivity and sustainable development.

Goal 5.

Achieve gender equality and empower women and girls.

5.1 - End all forms of discrimination against all women and girls everywhere.

(...)

5.5 - Ensure women’s full and effective participation and equal opportunities for leadership at all levels of decision-making in political, economic and public life.

(...)

5.a - Undertake reforms to give women equal rights to economic resources, as well as access to ownership and control over land and other forms of property, financial services, inheritance and natural resources, in accordance with national laws.

5.b - Enhance the use of enabling technology, in particular information and communications technology, to promote the empowerment of women.

5.c - Adopt and strengthen sound policies and enforceable legislation for the promotion of gender equality and the empowerment of all women and girls at all levels.

Goal 16.

Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all and build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels.

(...)

16.6 - Develop effective, accountable and transparent institutions at all levels.

16.7 - Ensure responsive, inclusive, participatory and representative decision-making at all levels.

16.8 - Broaden and strengthen the participation of developing countries in the institutions of global governance.

16.b - Promote and enforce non-discriminatory laws and policies for sustainable development

Goal 17.

Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the Global Partnership for Sustainable Development.

(...)

17.16 Enhance the Global Partnership for Sustainable Development, complemented by multi-stakeholder partnerships that mobilize and share knowledge, expertise, technology and financial resources, to support the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals in all countries, in particular developing countries

17.17 Encourage and promote effective public, public-private and civil society partnerships, building on the experience and resourcing strategies of partnerships.

Table 1 - An overview of the SDGs covered by the “EIC Communities” project

Source: [Transforming our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, 2015](#)

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The EIC portfolio features innovators from 45 different nations, including both European member states and associated countries from across the globe, with 20% of EIC Accelerator funding allotted to woman-led companies (*EIC Impact Report, 2022*). CoP stakeholders must also reflect this variety in gender, nationality, and cultural background, and no communication and community-building activities can be undertaken without accounting for the diversity of the engaged stakeholders.

The aim of this report is to provide a knowledge base and a set of good practices on how to build and promote inclusive communities and to guide the consortium members on how to communicate with and engage stakeholders while promoting equality and respecting diversity.

The report will include a brief state of the art section on the consensus regarding the role of language and community-building practices towards fostering social sustainability, as well as a review of the standard good practices currently adopted in these areas. The following section will review a series of case studies implemented by consortium members involved in the EIC Communities project, in order to integrate previously established good practises into the upcoming activities. This theoretical framework and review of past experiences will provide the basis for a series of practical guidelines, detailed in a subsequent section, which should be the basis for the project's communication output, supporting the creation of inclusive and accessible content, as well as the activities and materials developed to animate the CoPs.

2. State of the Art

2.1. Promoting social sustainability and diversity through language

Language plays an invaluable role in the effort to dismantle systems of inequality. The words and images with which we choose to communicate can help us reframe stories, deconstruct stereotypes, challenge structures, and empower marginalised communities. Inclusive language, whether verbal or visual, goes beyond politeness or political correctness. It is, rather, a tool to reshape reality itself by influencing attitudes, behaviours, and perceptions (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2022).

Thus, language is an indisputable asset in any organisation's commitment to social sustainability. Although often lacking a uniform definition and criticised as an empty signifier, this dimension of sustainability is usually defined by the commitment to the basic values of equity and the protection of all human rights (political, civil, economic, social and cultural). By upholding the rights of marginalised people, social sustainability contributes to cultural and social inclusivity, encouraging integration and creating solid, diverse communities in which all segments of the population may see improvements in their quality of life (McGuinn et al., 2020).

The role of language as a promoter of social sustainability is implied in the style guides of countless organisations, which already include guidelines and tips on how to avoid phrasing and that perpetuates social stereotypes and assigns roles to specific layers of individuals. The European Commission's Style Guide (2020) dedicates a brief section to the topic, emphasising the role of gender-neutral, person-first and other types of inclusive language.

Some organisations, however, have gone further and developed dedicated documents that focus exclusively on the use of inclusive language. Rather than simple style guides, these are resources for policymakers, media and organisation members interested in making their communication more inclusive. Some, such as the European Institute for Gender Equality's Toolkit on Gender-sensitive Communication (2020) focus on addressing specific issues, namely gender inequality. Oxfam's Inclusive Language Guide (2023) assigns the "seven feminist principles for language use" the capacity to empower, not only women and girls, but

all marginalised communities, including people with disabilities, people from low-income countries and communities, LGTBQIA+ and trans individuals, migrants and Black people, Indigenous people and People of Colour (BIPOC).

The present report will follow the good examples built by these organisations, providing guidelines for language that reflect power issues touching on gender, race, sexuality, disability and even geographical difference, in order to fully engage the diversity of the EIC portfolio and its community of stakeholders.

2.1.1 A note on the use of English

No project with an international scope can truly consider the topic of inclusivity without acknowledging the challenges posed by the use of English as an international language (EIL).

EIL is used for cross-cultural communication by both native and bilingual English speakers. It can be used both locally, between speakers of diverse cultures and languages within the same country and, most importantly for the scope of the project, in a global context, between speakers from different countries (Seidlhofer, 2003).

The very use of an international language has political implications. Using English for cross-cultural communication reflects changes in the world market, as well as scientific, cultural and media developments, but also its colonial legacy. Brutt-Griffler, quoted by Seidlhofer (2003), however, cautions against thinking of this phenomenon as a sort of “linguistic imperialism”, as EIL has often been used a tool for anti-imperialistic efforts throughout history. EIL also transcends the role of an elite *lingua franca*, as it is often learned by people in various strata of society, rather than being the purview of a socio-economic elite.

Nonetheless, native English speakers are obviously at an advantage when using EIL, as “correct” English is often conceptualised as English as Native Language (ENL) with all its idioms and fixed expressions, creating a power imbalance when using EIL.

In order to comply with the European Commission's style guide (2020) and ensure consistency across texts, all project outputs should follow standard usage English of the United Kingdom and Ireland.

However, efforts should be made to accommodate all levels of EIL speakers. Simple, objective language that reaches people with several levels of proficiency and detaches the concept of “fluent” from “native-sounding” should be adopted.

2.2. Visual representation

If language shapes reality, so do the images we chose to communicate with. Images can either challenge or reinforce existing bias, erase or empower people.

When providing guidelines for image selection, organisations often do not elaborate very much in writing, choosing instead to provide examples of what constitute good choices and images to avoid. The European Institute for Gender Equality’s Toolkit on Gender-sensitive Communication (2020) and the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime’s Guide on gender-inclusive communication (2022) both follow this approach, by displaying examples of images that assign stereotypical professional roles to women and men and should be avoided. The second document, however, goes further by explaining and exemplifying how images should, if possible, include not only a variety of genders but also people of different abilities, cultural and religious expressions.

In a cross-cultural project that seeks to engage stakeholders from a variety of different backgrounds and reinforce the EIC’s commitment to gender equality, diversity in visual representation plays a crucial role. We must use images that reflect the diversity of the communities we seek to engage, which span across nationalities, ethnicities, genders and various other identities, for the sake of accuracy. But these choices play an additional role, as lack of representation in imagery often becomes a self-fulfilling prophecy: people who do not see themselves represented in specific roles cannot conceive of ever achieving them. This is supported by the data in *Taking the Lead: Girls and Young Women on changing the Face of Leadership* (Geena Davis Institute on Gender & Media, 2019), a comprehensive report that drew its conclusions from surveys and focus groups conducted with over 10 thousand girls from 19 countries across the globe. In this report, the presence of female role models was identified as crucial for girls to aspire to leadership positions in their community. KPMG’s *Women’s Leadership Study: Moving Women Forward into Leadership Roles* further supports these conclusions, by revealing that six in 10 women of the over 3000 they

surveyed found it difficult to even see themselves in leadership positions. Representation through role models is not only visual, of course, but the image of a member of a community depicted in a leadership or otherwise previously “unreachable” role can be a first step towards unlocking aspirations.

When it comes to providing guidelines for images, this report will build on the good practices promoted by the organisations quoted throughout this section, and include examples of what to search for in an image and what to avoid.

2.3. Engaging diversity through accessibility and parity

Despite the pivotal role played by language, both verbal and visual, in promoting social sustainability, community building efforts can incorporate additional measures to create inclusive environments.

The Inclusive Communication Guidelines published by the Directorate-General for Communication of the European Parliament (2019) go beyond providing guidance for verbal and visual language in documents and promotion materials, extending the use of inclusive communication principles to events and public debates. These include physical and digital accessibility in events and activities.

For physical events, an active effort must be made to ensure accessible venues for people with disabilities and provide all the necessary information on available services (how to book mobility scooters, the possibility of sign-language interpretation, etc). There must also be a commitment to ensuring web accessibility: all websites must incorporate good practices to improve user experience, including providing alternative text on all digital content and using Camel Case (capitalising the first letter of every word) on hashtags whenever possible, in order to make the content readable for people with visual impairments and/or dyslexia, Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) and other types of neurodivergence.

Lastly, communication efforts that ensure inclusive language and visual representation are of no use unless an effort is made to ensure actual representation. While the lack of gender parity and people from minorities in science and innovation is often bred earlier, through socio-economic factors that must be dismantled with policy efforts, we must commit to ensuring adequate levels of gender parity and geographic diversity in the speakers and

D1.7 Knowledge base on how to build and promote sustainable and inclusive communities around EIC portfolios participants featured in the thematic workshops, Portfolio Days and activities organised under the Future Tech Weeks. 13

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3. Case Studies

While reviewing the literature is essential to ensure compliance with current good practices and accessibility measures, practical case studies can offer further insight on how to implement them. The EIC Communities project can leverage the past experiences of its consortium members, which have a proven track record of accomplishing projects with strong inclusivity and representation components.

3.1 The W4RES Project: forging a space for women in the RHC sector

[W4RES](#) was a three-year-EU-funded project within the H2020 programme, which aimed at scaling up the involvement of women in the market deployment and uptake of Renewable Heating and Cooling (RHC) solutions via replicable support measures tested and validated across eight European countries (Belgium, Bulgaria, Denmark, Germany, Greece, Italy, Norway, and Slovakia).

The basic concept of the project derived from the recognition that women hold great promise as agents of change, helping us make faster progress toward 2030 climate and energy goals. The project provided practical guidelines to replicate and recommendations for well-informed policy, cost-effective support schemes, and funding frameworks tailored to the requirements of key EU issues such as policy, entrepreneurship, and societal needs.

The project started on 1 November 2020 and ended its activities on 31 October 2023. W4RES was coordinated by Q-PLAN International Advisors PC (Greece) with APRE - Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea (Italy) CiviESCO (Italy), Energy Agency of Plovdiv (Bulgaria), European Center for Women and Technology (Norway), European Green Cities (Denmark), The Association of European Renewable Energy Research Centres (Belgium), Hochschule fur Technik Stuttgart (Germany), Pedal consulting (Slovakia), Steinbeis (Germany), WECF (The Netherlands), White research (Belgium).

3.1.1 What was implemented?

The project started with a deep dive into framework conditions and regional specificities of 8 diverse yet representative markets in Europe, assessing enablers and barriers to RHC uptake. Building on gender-disaggregated insights from market actors and stakeholders as well as successful cases of women leading RHC projects, W4RES developed a suite of flexible and cost-effective support measures with high reapplication potential. It then

deployed its measures on the field offering technical and business support to cut down project development timings and efforts as well as to sidestep legal, institutional and financial challenges, setting in motion feasible and sustainable business models fit to market. In parallel, the project empowered decision-makers to leverage a gender perspective into their projects and policies to improve acceptance, while raising awareness to foster demand for RHC. Along the way, a gender-responsive monitoring and evaluation framework gauged the performance and impact of the implemented measures, providing with the intel required to turn them from solutions fit for a set of local challenges to integrated solutions that can address diverse policy and market needs across Europe. The project used this intel as a catalyst to foster co-creation, mutual learning and international cooperation for frameworks more conducive to RHC uptake at local, regional national and EU level, based on cost-effective support schemes and lower financing costs for RHC facilities. In the process, W4RES coordinated the actions with relevant initiatives and offered tools to facilitate the reapplication of the project's results, ensuring their long-term sustainability as viable solutions to supporting RHC uptake.

3.1.2 Best practices and lessons learned concerning gender inclusivity

W4RES had a dual objective:

1. enhance the market adoption of RHC solutions
2. increase the active involvement of women in the RHC sector.

This initiative was a timely response to the ongoing energy and climate crisis in Europe, where research has indicated that investing in RHC technologies represents a cost-effective and environmentally friendly approach.

The project developed a set of policy recommendations ([D5.4 Policy recommendations](#)) that allow for an increase of the gender inclusivity in the referenced sector, but that could be adapted and also applied to other innovative sectors in a replicability perspective:

1. *to lay the foundation for a gender-balanced RHC sector that not only addresses current disparities but also nurtures opportunities for future generations. The key aspects discussed are strategies to promote girls' access to STEM education and to facilitate closer collaboration between educational institutions and industry stakeholders;*

2. *creating a more inclusive workplace within the RHC sector. This set includes the establishment of gender quotas, provision of business and technical support for women entrepreneurs, the implementation of gender- and family-friendly workplace policies, and the introduction of robust structures for reporting unwanted behaviour in the industry;*
3. *to promote gender equity across the RHC sector by advocating for gender-smart policies, the collection of gender-disaggregated data, gender-inclusive communication strategies, and the establishment of more gender-inclusive energy cooperatives;*
4. *focus on institutionalising awareness about gender mainstreaming in the RHC sector. It emphasises raising awareness about gender barriers in the industry and the mandatory implementation of gender-smart training for industry stakeholders;*
5. *focus on dedicated funding opportunities for women-led projects, gender-just budgeting quotas, and greater female participation in RHC research, aiming to remove financial barriers and boost women's participation in the field.*

W4RES also developed a practical toolkit ([D5.5. Replication Guide and Toolkit](#)), tested across the abovementioned eight European countries to scale up the involvement of women in the market deployment and uptake of RHC solutions, bringing together expertise on renewable energy sources research and advocacy, innovative business model development and women advocacy.

The recommended strategies were:

1. Setting up Regional Hubs to involve stakeholders in the RHC sector, to share knowledge and to act as facilitators for a diversity of projects and activities.
2. Providing Business, Innovation and Technical Support Services to women-led innovation projects within the field of RHC.
3. Setting up Capacity Building Programmes consisting of seminars (train-of-trainers) and webinars (dissemination knowledge to a wider international audience) in order to strengthen the capacities of the business sector and

decision-makers on gender mainstreaming and women empowerment in the RHC.

4. Organising Co-creation Workshops to bring together key stakeholders (representing authorities, institutions, industry and citizens) in co-defining the best strategy towards supporting women's leading role in accelerating RHC market uptake.
5. Offering Mutual Learning Workshops to provide unique opportunities for informal exchange of good practices between countries and representatives of different sectors, as well as to facilitate international cooperation.
6. Running Hackathons to involve regional stakeholders (RHC market actors, authorities, social organisations and researchers) in better understanding the given country's specific situation regarding barriers to the uptake of RHC technologies and the women involvement in the sector, and based on this to develop an action plan.
7. Creating Awareness Raising Campaigns to communicate about the importance of engaging women in the RHC sector.
8. Organising Networking events to help women entrepreneurs and researchers establish and exploit synergies with other organisations.
9. Implementing the Policy Briefs in order to help create a more competitive, inclusive and gender responsive RHC landscape in the EU.

In conclusion, the W4RES project developed a methodology and tools to support the inclusion of women in the RHC sector. The sustainability of these solutions is guaranteed by the adoption and applicability of the methodology to other innovative and technological fields that need to increase or boost the inclusion of women or marginalized communities.

3.2 The Women Leadership Programme: boosting female-led excellence in science and business

The [Woman Leadership Programme \(WLP\)](#) offers networking and training opportunities to female researchers and entrepreneurs supported by the EIC, as well as to female innovators backed by the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT). From the 2nd cohort onwards, the programme was also extended to Women TechEU awardees.

The programme falls under the scope of the EIC's Business Acceleration Services, offering tools, knowledge and connections that can nurture and expand the potential of the participating innovators, allowing them to excel in science and business. The goal of the WLP is to boost the role of women in innovation and tech, supporting the EIC's efforts to change the status quo and bridge the gender gap in working teams, but especially when it comes to leadership positions in research and business.

The programme was first launched in October 2021 and is set to start implementing the activities under its 4th cohort in February 2024. EurA AG (member of the EIC Communities consortium) led the implementation of the first three WLP cohorts: the 1st cohort took place between October 2021 to March 2022, the 2nd cohort was implemented from May 2022 to October 2022 and the 3rd cohort took place between April 2023 and June 2023.

3.2.1 What was implemented?

The resources offered to participating innovators included:

1. A tailored-made journey of **eight training sessions** per cohort approaching fundamental topics (How to create and scale up a company) and highly specific subjects (How to create a strategy to go international);
2. Five engaging **networking events** to foster the contact of the participants with key players in different thematics delivered during the 1st cohort, with seven additional events under the 2nd cohort, enriching the experience and heightening the visibility of the participants;
3. A **mentoring scheme** with a focus on the personal and professional perspectives. The activity was delivered by experienced and trusted Mentors from a great pool of reputable professionals and repeated in all implemented cohorts;

4. A **business coaching scheme** with the Pool of Coaches from the EIC Accelerator Programme to assist the group of participants in their specific business challenges and provide insight into their entrepreneurship potential.

The programme also included the live streaming of one **launching session** and three **award ceremonies** to further promote the initiative and boost the profiles of participating entrepreneurs, both on the mentor and mentee sides. Testimonies under each cohort were then added to future open calls for participants.

Participants from past cohorts were also invited to sign up for an Alumni Group in the [EIC Community](#) platform, the EIC's online one-stop-shop to register for EIC services and events, search for like-minded entrepreneurs, explore business opportunities with EIC peers and explore many other opportunities.

3.2.2 Best practises learned on inclusivity

The first three cohorts of the WLP programme achieved remarkable rates of engagement, with **+350 applications** for participants and **+600 applications** for mentors. These numbers were integral to the success of the programme, allowing for a rich pool of mentors that participants could choose from and ensuring a diversity of background profiles amongst the participants.

The success of WLP resulted in some crucial lessons learned, which can be turned into best practises and considered when implementing the activities under the EIC Communities project.

1. Foster communities and have individuals empower each other – The connections established between mentors and mentees were at the core of the programme's success, abiding by the feminist principle "nothing about us without us" (Oxfam, 2023) by putting the empowerment of female entrepreneurs in the hands of their peers.

Keeping beneficiaries engaged through the alumni group in the EIC Community was also a way of ensuring each cohort's legacy, by keeping female entrepreneurs engaged with each other and willing to network and explore opportunities together even after the end of the mentoring phase.

It is empowering to be “looking around at a room full of women and knowing that I can just turn to any woman and be inspired and in awe of what they do”.

Perine Fleurya, Co-founder of Biosphere Solar and WLP alumna

The idea that female entrepreneurs should be able to support each other and complement each other's skills was at the heart of the concept of the mentorship scheme. To achieve this, mentors were invited to create a profile in the B2Match platform. Each mentor could present herself, her experience and add what she was looking for in a potential mentee. Mentees then ranked their preferred mentors, who would receive these manifestations of interest and select their sole mentee.

“There isn't a human being on earth - man or woman, expert or not - that has all the answers all the time. So instead of feeling the pressure to know-it-all, we can embrace the learning journey we are all on and state our commitment to keep looking for the answers - on our own or together with the people who are asking us the questions.”

Eva Dimitrova, Director at Founder Institute Cologne and WLP mentor

2. Deliver knowledge – Across the programme's several cohorts, 80% of the participants on the mentee side indicated relevant improvements in areas such as pitching, time management, personal branding, negotiation and other market-strategic skills covered by the programme. By delivering knowledge, WLP supports innovators with the practical tools to carve out their role in the market, which can translate directly into higher success rates for female entrepreneurs and boost the role of women in innovation and deep tech.

“I strongly believe in the benefits of mentoring and business coaching but, as a startup founder, this is usually the thing you have the least funding for, it's the last thing you spend money on. I think [WLP] is a crucial endeavor and a very valuable programme.”

Catherine Schreiber, co-founder of Advitos and WLP alumna

3. Boost visibility of the participants and share their success stories – As discussed during the state-of-the-art section, the presence of female role models plays a crucial role in encouraging women to aspire to leadership roles (KPMG, 2015). Promoting the success stories under the programmes creates role models for current WLP participants, for prospective participants and even for female entrepreneurs in the EIC Community that may not have a direct connection to WLP.

Throughout the programme, the WLP team made a continuous effort to centre the testimonies of former participants in the communication materials. Aside from the merit of this approach towards the effective promotion of the programme, borrowing some of the credibility of first-person testimonies, centring the voices of female entrepreneurs emphasizes the fact that women can be key players in the deep tech ecosystem and promotes the stories of the female trailblazers already leading innovation in their fields.

“I am committed to this programme because I want to improve my capabilities, but I also want to help change things for others! I think the Programme boosts my confidence to take action towards what I want to achieve.”

Joana Vaz Cardoso, Chief Scientific and Technical Officer at Ophiomics and WLP alumna

To sum up, the lessons learned during the implementation of the first three cohorts of the WLP provided key insights on how to empower female entrepreneurs and build sustainable communities of participants. These will be fundamental in creating actionable guidelines to ensure the inclusivity and sustainability of the activities under the EIC Communities project.

3.3 The Better Incubation: Innovation Ecosystem for Social Change

[Better Incubation](#) is a 2-year programme (2021 – 2023) powered by the LIAISE project, funded under the European Union Programme for Employment and Social Innovation. The project aims at fostering inclusive and social entrepreneurship in Europe by mobilising and empowering business support organisations (BSOs, including EUBICs, IHUBs, investors for impact) with capacities to effectively help the social enterprises and potential entrepreneurs from underrepresented groups to access financial tools and and increase their businesses’ chances of survival and growth. Overall, Better Incubation aims to trigger an “eco-systemic” change by bringing incubation and business support services closer to the society and contribute to societal needs through entrepreneurship and self-employment based on job creation, skills development and provision of opportunities for unemployed and vulnerable people to fully participate in the society and economy.

Better Incubation programme was a one-of-a-kind opportunity to engage and achieve the transformational impact of the business support ecosystem, with three partner networks,

EBN, IHUB and EVPA, working together towards a sustainable “better incubation ecosystem”, open to all kind of entrepreneurs.

The objective of this project is:

1. Provide BSOs with adequate knowledge and tools to pilot incubation programmes for social and inclusive enterprises/would be entrepreneurs, namely women, migrants and refugees, people with disabilities, seniors, youth.
2. Enhance the diversity/inclusiveness of BSOs.
3. Improve the tracking/performance of BSOs.
4. Encourage the scaling of impact driven entrepreneurship across Europe.

3.3.1 What was implemented?

1. CAPACITY BUILDING FOR BSOs >> Provide BSOs with knowledge and tools to pilot incubation programmes for social and inclusive entrepreneurs. This is done through creating and enabling 5 thematic Communities of Practice (CoPs) and delivering capacity building online programme to BSOs.
2. CULTURAL PARADIGM SHIFT >> Engaging multiple stakeholders to shape together a more inclusive and impact driven ecosystem. Making sure that the results of the project are applied by the partners and then validated by the national and European ecosystem players.
3. MONITORING, ASSESSMENT AND LEARNING >> Developing, prototyping and implementing a shared assessment framework to measure and assess the impact of incubation programmes run by the participating members.
4. DISSEMINATION AND STAKEHOLDERS MOBILISATION >> Ensuring coordinated communication and disseminate the outcomes of Better Incubation across the three networks. Supporting the transfer of good practices through reaching out to other business support organisations across Europe.

3.3.2 Results

The LIAISE project contributed to the EU social and employment policy, namely addressing the policy theme: promoting social economy and inclusive entrepreneurship.

LIAISE - Linking Incubation Actors for Inclusive and Social Entrepreneurship was based on the premise that business support organisations (BSOs), as fundamental players of

entrepreneurship ecosystems, can extend their contribution to solving complex social and economic challenges, through fostering social innovation and inclusive entrepreneurship. This was done through initiating an ecosystemic change by bringing incubation and business support services closer to the whole society and giving unemployed and vulnerable people an opportunity to fully participate in the economy.

The project framework addressed three levels of activities which led to the paradigm shift in the European incubation ecosystem:

1. individual-entrepreneurs level (10 entrepreneurs representing the targeted groups involved in the CoPs; 133 entrepreneurs/would be entrepreneurs enrolled in the inclusive incubation pilots; 3 companies selected to benefit from the Better Incubation Scaling Programme),
2. organisational/incubators level (21 BSOs involved in the CoPs; 140 organisations in the trainings; 9 in the delivery of the Better incubation scaling programme; 15 in the preparation and implementation of 15 regional policy workshops)
3. systemic-policy level (351 stakeholders participated in 15 regional policy workshops and 22 stakeholders in the EU workshop in Brussels).

3.3.3 Best practises learned on inclusivity

1. Better Incubation established 5 communities of practice (CoP). <https://betterincubation.eu/communities-of-practice/>
2. Better Incubation CoPs represent a unique opportunity to exchange practical knowledge on how to best support entrepreneurs and would-be entrepreneurs from under- represented groups in Europe.
3. By engaging and working with peers, social actors, entrepreneurs from vulnerable groups and experts, European business support organisations (incubators and accelerators) research best practices and co-design new approaches in the field of social and inclusive entrepreneurship support.
4. The Better Incubation CoPs' methodologies, processes and tools, and the lessons learned from this action informed the design phase of Deepsync CoPs.

4. Guidelines

4.1 Language

4.1.1 Avoid gendered pronouns and nouns when the subject's gender is unknown or irrelevant

In many texts, authors still revert to the masculine pronoun “he” when referring to subjects whose gender is unknown. Similarly, many nouns for occupations and roles still assume the gender of those who hold them.

One should choose gender neutral language to:

1. Avoid re-enforcing stereotypes by attributing stereotypical actions and roles to a specific gender;
2. Not erase men, women, or individuals outside of the gender binary from the conversation;
3. Not misgender people.

If the participant is selected, **he** must abide by the rules of the group.

For the benefit of **mankind**.

The **spokesman/chairman** of the association announced the decision today.

If the participant is selected, **they** must abide by the rules of the group.

For the benefit of **humankind**.

The **spokesperson/chairperson** of the association announced the decision today.

4.1.2 Consider using person-first language to avoid stigmatising people with disabilities and health conditions

People with disabilities, physical or mental health conditions have to deal with a dominant culture that excludes, devalues and limits their potential (Oxfam, 2020). This phenomenon, known as **ableism**, greatly affects their ability to access education, employment and adequate support for their needs.

Although policy adjustments and societal progress is needed to adequately deal with these obstacles, combating the stigma can start with the language we use to refer to people.

Person-first language is recommended when dealing with the topics of disability, mental or physical health, in order to:

1. Avoid defining the person by their illness or disability;
2. Place the humanity, value and autonomy of people with disabilities front and centre by emphasising that they are a human being first;
3. Reduce the risk of resorting to outdated and stigmatising terms riddled with negative connotations.

In order to avoid inaccuracies when referring to specific disabilities, mental or physical illnesses, it is also recommended to do **proper research on a case by case basis**. The medical field is constantly evolving, and it is crucial not to refer to outdated and possibly stigmatising diagnoses when telling the stories of those who live with them.

The person was **wheelchair-bound**.

This policy will have a lot of impact on **AIDS victims**.

The person had a **mobility impairment/used a wheelchair**.

This policy will have a lot of impact on **people living with HIV**.

The **disabled** should have the same rights as **normal/healthy people**.

The person was **manic-depressive**.

People with disabilities should have the same rights as **non-disabled people**.

The person had **bipolar disorder**.

4.1.3 Respect diversity in sexuality and gender identity

One should mind terms that might erase or disrespect LGBTQ+ people or perpetuate transphobia. Avoiding slurs or derogatory language should be a given in professional, respectful communication. Yet, it is also important to avoid resorting to **heteronormative** stereotypes, meaning conventions that assume that heterosexuality is the norm, or to equating sex and gender.

It is essential to:

1. Avoid making heterosexuality the default, therefore implying that all LGBTQ+ people are deviations from the norm;
2. Respect the identities of trans people;
3. Mention someone's sexuality or trans identity only when relevant to the topic at hand, rather than as a defining characteristic.

The **LGBTQ+** acronym refers to a spectrum of identities including lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer and other people who are not heterosexual and cisgender¹ (Stonewall, 2023). While alternative spellings for this acronym are available, such as LGBTQIA+, which includes the initials for the intersex and asexual communities, these can be used interchangeably. The focus should be on not excluding the T, which is sometimes done in trans-exclusionary materials (Oxfam, 2020).

The term **Queer**, originally a slur, was also reclaimed in the late 1980s and is now often adopted to refer to those who do not identify as heterosexual or cisgender (Stonewall, 2023). Under the scope of the project, however, we advise avoiding the use of this term in isolation, as it still carries derogatory connotations within some age groups and cultures.

¹ **Cisgender** - people who identify with the gender they were assigned at birth.

Employees indicated that the long hours often caused strain on their relationships with their **wives**.

The **gay** community.

Maria was **born a man/is biologically male**.

Employees indicated that the long hours often caused strain on their relationships with their **spouses/partners**.

The **LGBTQ+** community.

Maria was **assigned male at birth (AMAB)**.

4.1.4 Avoid language which perpetuate stereotypes about ethnicities, nationalities and cultures

EIC beneficiaries come from mostly EU member states, but also associated countries under Horizon Europe. When communication under the project, one must take into account that Europe is not a cultural or ethnic monolith, and that EIC stakeholders can also come from regions outside of the continent. Although we resort to English as a common language (ECL) for the reasons detailed in the state-of-the-art section, special care must be adopted in order to ensure respect for all cultures and ethnic minorities².

The rules to consider are the following:

1. The nationality of a company or EIC project can be mentioned to the extent that it helps explain the national context under which it was established.
2. The nationality/ethnicity of an entrepreneur should be mentioned only if relevant to the story they are telling about themselves. While a person's ethnicity and nationality can be a part of their story, they should not be taken as their defining characteristic.

² Ethnic minority – According to the Onxford English dictionary, “a group of people from a particular culture or of a particular race living in a country where the main group is of a different culture or race”.

3. European citizens are European citizens regardless of religion or ethnic origin.
4. Avoid mentioning nationalities or ethnicities as a monolith, as these communities often include people of a variety of classes, cultures and political interests.

A Muslim citizen.

Kofi is an EIC entrepreneur, CEO of company X, based in Norway. **He is of Ghanaian origin.**

The Polish people voted for party X.

A French citizen.

Kofi is an EIC entrepreneur, CEO of company X, based in Norway. He **explains that his idea for the company actually began during his childhood trips to Ghana, where his parents were born.**

40% of Polish People voted for party X.

3.4 Visual Representation

In order to achieve its aim to create diverse, inclusive communities, the project must use images that represent them, and opt for images that challenge stereotypes whenever possible.

4.2.1 In group representations, prioritise images that show gender balance

Whenever referring to mixed groups or groups of people whose gender is never mentioned, avoid images that only show people of the same gender. This is particularly important if you are depicting activities often associated with one particular gender, such as a corporate boardroom full of men or a playground with only female caretakers.

4.2.2 Try to find images with diverse subjects and consider whether your efforts go beyond tokenism

Whenever possible, images should be diverse in terms of the gender, disability, age and ethnicity of those represented.

It is, however, important to monitor the use of so-called “tokenism”. This practise consists of making symbolic and cosmetic efforts to show diversity by including a small number of people from underrepresented groups in promotional materials, but to do so only to create an *appearance* of diversity (Directorate-General for Communication, 2019). While visual representation is important, diverse representation is not accurate or fully impactful unless practical efforts are undertaken to translate it into reality. Therefore, stock images with

diverse groups should be used whenever possible, but the real goal should be to make the actual images that are captured during the project (family pictures taken during events, materials telling the stories of EIC beneficiaries, etc etc) as diverse as possible by ensuring inclusive participation in programme activities.

With ethnic minorities making up about 10% of the EU's population (Islam & Woodford, 2022), it is imperative to assure that images and selection of event participants reflect this reality at the very least.

4.2.3 Try to pick images that challenge gender stereotypes

Images that depict women in positions of power or performing physically demanding jobs, as well as men in caretaker roles and professions, can be powerful assets to make sure that one is not perpetuating stereotypes.

4.3 Community Management

4.3.1 Diversity and inclusion in community building activities

The “EIC Communities” project should incorporate both a strong commitment to gender parity, ethnic diversity, and inclusion of people with disabilities, as well as respect for excellence and rejection of “tokenism”, as described in point 3.2.2 of this report.

To abide by these principles, community building efforts should respect the following guidelines:

1. Each **CoP must feature** a minimum of 50 women-lead companies/projects.
2. Women must feature in **at least a third of EIC project stories**, including testimonial videos, articles and press releases, to make sure that these reflect their real rate of participation in the activities organised under the project.
3. Working and co-creation groups should have **geographical diversity in their clustering criteria**, to promote fruitful exchanges between EIC beneficiaries from different backgrounds and ensure that the project is welcoming and accessible to innovators from across Europe and associated countries.

The EIC’s Statement on Gender & Diversity (2021) already accounts for some of the measures that may be taken to improve the underrepresentation of women in EIC initiatives, such as the prioritisation of women-led companies for EIC jury pitches and investment partnerships with the EIC Fund, but it recognises that “work is needed to understand, monitor and take action to promote other aspects of diversity in EIC supported projects”.

Under the scope of this particular project, the efforts to include ethnic minorities and people with disabilities will focus on making digital events and materials, as well as in-person activities, as accessible and welcoming as possible. The guidelines to ensure this will be detailed in the upcoming sections.

4.3.2 Digital accessibility

Virtual, digital events such as 35 out of the 37 ones predicted under the scope of the programme eliminate some accessibility concerns for people with reduced mobility, facilitate participation from people across the globe and reduce the environmental footprint of the initiative by eliminating unnecessary traveling.

However, some factors must still be taken into account when making sure that people with disabilities can participate in programme workshops, Portfolio Days, co-creation sessions, Future Tech Weeks and remaining activities on equal terms. Project materials can also be accommodated to people with visual or hearing impairments.

While many in-depth guides on web/digital accessibility are available online (Web Accessibility Initiative, 2023), one must make sure to take at least the following basic rules into account:

- 1. Ensure that captions are available on promotional videos and online events.** For virtual events organised through Zoom, you can ensure this by allowing the use of [live transcription](#), which can be useful to be people with hearing impairments or who use English as a second language.
- 2. Always provide alternative text on pictures and digital content.** Alternative text is essential for screen readers, software programmes used by people with visual impairments or learning disabilities to navigate text and/or image content.
- 3. Use Camel Case** (capitalisation of the first letter in every word) in hashtags on social media and other mediums to improve readability.
- 4. Use colour contrasts** between text and background to improve readability.
- 5. Avoid moving, flashing or blinking elements**, as these can cause seizures in people with photosensitive epilepsy.
- 6. Incorporate responsive web design** to make sure that your page is accessible through a variety of different devices.

By adhering to these recommendations, you can ensure the project's commitment to the European Commission's directive for [web accessibility](#).

A preview of the website announcing the future DeepSync platform, powered by the “EIC Communities” project, featuring:

- A contrasting color scheme.
- Responsive web design.

Preview the website here:

<https://deepsync.eu/>

4.3.3 In-person event accessibility

The “EIC Communities” project will organise two in-person events, including at least one in-person co-creation workshop. In order to ensure that all participants have equal opportunity to access the venue and feel safe and welcome during the event, the organisation must ensure that the following conditions are met:

1. Event **venues and visitor areas should be accessible for people with disabilities**. While different EU member states have different legislation and accessibility requirements, the organisation should at least ensure that the event venues are wheelchair accessible and that people with mobility restrictions are able to navigate them.
2. Catering **should always include vegan options** for people who do not eat animal products, both out of respect for health-related dietary restrictions, personal choices and even cultural and religious mandates. Whenever possible, allergens and animal-based ingredients should be disclosed in labels next to the catering items.

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3. Registration forms for in-person events should include **questions on allergies, mobility limitations** to identify possible extra accommodations that may be needed for participants.

* Do you have any mobility restrictions?

If you are using a wheelchair or have any other type of mobility restriction, please specify.

If not, simply type "no" on this field.

This field is required.

* Do you have any allergies?

Please specify if you suffer from any serious food allergies or have any other type of dietary restriction (vegan, vegetarian, do not eat pork, etc).

If not, simply type "no" on this field.

This field is required.

5. Conclusions

5.1 Conclusion of the Report

Throughout this report, we aimed to provide a resource for those working to promote sustainable and inclusive community building under the “EIC Communities” project. We drew from state-of-the-art best practises on language, visual representation and accessibility to establish actionable guidelines and provide examples on how to conduct communication and community building work.

While the practical implications that the content of the report/knowledge base should have on the project’s activities has been stressed throughout the text, there are particular tasks and work packages that would be affected by this research:

- **WP2, Task 2.1** – The established guidelines and best practises should be taken into account during the creation of the CoPs, by ensuring geographic and gender balance when selecting the stakeholders to engage in each group;
- **WP2, Task 2.2, 2.3, 2.4 & 2.5** – Guidelines for visual materials and language should be respected when producing materials, reports and organising events to animate the CoPs. The concern should be to make the activities accommodating and accessible to all participants.
- **WP3, Task 3.1** – The guidelines detailed in this report should be reflected in the Dissemination and Communication Plan (D&C), as well as any materials developed under its scope.
- **WP3, Task 3.2** – Digital accessibility principles should be taken into account in any future updates of the DeepSync platform, as well as on the promotion undertaken through the project’s social media accounts. The language used on all digital content should also comply with the project guidelines.

The content of the report should help all of those working on these tasks to ensure that their output complies with the inclusivity and sustainability concerns integral to the “EIC Communities” programme.

5.2 Limitations

It is, however, important to acknowledge the limitations of our work. Firstly, the report is heavily based on language, an evolving medium that is adapted and changed by the people who use it (Seidlhofer, 2003). This means that it may become outdated as new terms come into use and further conversations are led by grass-roots organisations working on gender parity, LGTQ+ rights, racial equality and disability advocacy. No community is a monolith, and many people who share characteristics disagree on how to refer to themselves. Oxfam's guide on inclusive communication (2021) expresses this contradiction. Although it draws on the work of several grass-roots organisations to advise against the use of the term "deaf", many associations and disability advocates in the United Kingdom, the country in which the document was prepared, such as the [British Deaf Association](#), still choose to identify as such.

Concepts of sexual orientation, gender identity and gender roles also vary greatly across cultures and communities. The terms and concepts expressed in the state-of-the art section of this report closely align with western definitions and subcultures, and might not be widely accepted or easily translated into South-Asian, African or other non-European contexts, from which a few of the programme's stakeholders might hail. Third genders, for example, exist across many non-western cultures, with the *hijras* in India and Bangladesh and the *two-spirit people* in Indigenous American tribes serving as examples (United Nations Development Programme, 2022). To refer to these people as trans women or trans men and fit them into western concepts might not necessarily be accurate.

Additionally, there might be some reluctance in using terms or images that indicate support of LGBTQ+ rights when engaging with communities and contexts in which religious fundamentalism is more common, both outside and within Europe. For useful tips on how to navigate these issues, one should turn to documents such as the United Nations Development Programme's handbook on *Advancing the Human Rights and Inclusion of LGBTQI People* (2022), which include universal and contextual arguments to promote LGBTQ+ rights according to the culture and religion one is engaging with. The same applies to the remaining issues that might clash with the values the European Commission is committed to: one must assure commitment to defending human rights in every context, even when adapting the message to the audience being engaged. We chose not to address

this topic in detail during the report due to the complexity of the matter and danger of venturing outside of the scope of the report but advise further research whenever cultural contexts might affect one's approach to ensuring inclusivity and acknowledge that the lack of focus on this topic is a limitation of the present document.

It is also nearly impossible to list all the instances in which one might encounter potentially sensitive language or imagery, and further research will almost always be needed to ensure that one is respecting the community being addressed or referred to. Our practical examples list the doubts that are most likely to be encountered when working on the project but are by no means all-inclusive.

Finally, the adoption of EIL as the language of the project's communication efforts implies the contradictions detailed in the state-of-the-art section. English is both a driver of inclusion and the language of a former colonial power, which leads the option to use it an ambiguous charge.

5.3 Checklist for inclusive and sustainable communication and community building

In the light of these limitations, the conclusions of this report are perhaps best formulated as questions that can guide one's work under the project, rather than strict dos and don'ts. If one is struggling on how to communicate or promote sustainability under the programme, one should refer to the following checklist:

Are you assuming a person's gender or using "man" as a signifier of humanity?
<input type="checkbox"/> If yes , you should use impersonal terms such as "one", the plural "they" or find non-gendered alternatives for the terms you are using.
<input type="checkbox"/> If not , you may proceed.
Is the person's gender identity/disability/ethnicity relevant to the story you're telling or event that you're organising? Do you need to know or mention this information to convey their experience or accommodate their needs?
<input type="checkbox"/> If yes , this can be mentioned and/or asked.
<input type="checkbox"/> If not , this should not be mentioned and/or asked.

Are you using language or imagery to associate an individual with roles and characteristics stereotypically assigned to their gender or ethnicity? Are you doing this without providing context about them as an individual?

- If **yes**, you should look for alternative terms and images.
- If **not**, you may proceed.

Are you using an encompassing term, such as deaf people, elderly people, etc to refer to a community?

- If **yes**, consider opting for person-first language and look into whether this term is widely accepted by members of said community.
- If **not**, there should be little danger of incurring in generalisations or using outdated terms.

Are you making sure that the project's web content is accessible to users with hearing and sight impediments and/or learning disabilities?

- If **yes**, you are complying with European Commission guidelines.
- If **not**, you should consult this [checklist](#) and adapt your content accordingly.

Are your in-person events being held in venues that are accessible for people with reduced mobility?

- If **yes**, keep the venue and check with the relevant participants whether further measures need to be taken to ensure their participation and comfort.
- If **not**, you should find an alternative option or make arrangements to ensure that the relevant participants can still access and navigate the venue.

For in-person events, is your catering provider serving vegan options and including allergen disclaimers?

- If **yes**, you are doing everything in your power to ensure the safety of the participants, but should still check if there are attendees with serious allergies that may be affected by cross-contamination.
- If **not**, you should pay extra attention to the dietary restrictions and allergies indicated by your attendees through their registration forms, and find alternatives for the specific people who may not be covered by the existing catering options.

References

Directorate-General for Communication, *Inclusive communication Guidelines*, 2019, retrieved from: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/contracts-and-grants/files/grants/media-and-events/2023/local-eye-2024/annex-III-inclusive-communication-guidelines-of-the-european-parliament.pdf>

European innovation Council, *EIC Impact Report 2022*, 2022, retrieved from: <https://eic.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-02/2022-EIC-Impact-Report-141222.pdf>

European Innovation Council, *Statement on Gender & Diversity in EIC*, 2021, retrieved from: https://eic.ec.europa.eu/news/statement-gender-diversity-eic-2021-06-03_en

European Innovation Council, *Work Programme 2024*, 2023, retrieved from: <https://eic.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-12/EIC-workprogramme-2024.pdf>

European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE), *Toolkit on Gender-sensitive Communication*, 2019, retrieved from: <https://eige.europa.eu/publications-resources/publications/toolkit-gender-sensitive-communication>

European Commission, *Style Guide*, 2020, retrieved from https://wikis.ec.europa.eu/download/attachments/6824833/commission_style_guide.pdf

Islam & Woodford, *Diversity and power in the European Union*, 2022, The European Policy Centre, retrieved from: https://epc.eu/content/PDF/2022/Jubilee_Papers/Jubilee_Think_Piece_Islam_Woodford.pdf

Geena Davis Institute on Gender & Media, *Taking the Lead: Girls and Young Women on changing the Face of Leadership*, 2019, Plan International, retrieved from: <https://plan-international.org/uploads/2022/01/takingthelead-fullreport-1.pdf>

KPMG, *KPMG Women's Leadership Study: Moving Women Forward into Leadership Roles*, 2015, retrieved from: <https://assets.kpmg.com/content/dam/kpmg/ph/pdf/ThoughtLeadershipPublications/KPMGWomensLeadershipStudy.pdf>

McGuinn, J. et al, *Social Sustainability – Concepts and Benchmarks*, Policy Department for Economic, Scientific and Quality of Life Policies, retrieved from: [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2020/648782/IPOL_STU\(2020\)648782_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2020/648782/IPOL_STU(2020)648782_EN.pdf)

Oxfam, *Inclusive Language Guide*, 2023, retrieved from: <https://policy-practice.oxfam.org/resources/inclusive-language-guide-621487/>

Seidlhofer, B., *A concept of International English and related issues: from real English to 'realistic English'?*, 2003, retrieved from: <https://rm.coe.int/a-concept-of-international-english-and-related-issues-from-real-englis/168088782f>

Stonewall. List of LGBTQ+ terms, 2023, retrieved from: <https://www.stonewall.org.uk/list-lgbtq-terms>

United Nations Development Programme, *Advancing the Human Rights and Inclusion of LGBTI People: A Handbook for Parliamentarians*, 2022, retrieved from: <https://www.undp.org/sites/g/files/zskgke326/files/2022-10/UNDP-Advancing-The-Human-Rights-and-Inclusion-of-LGBTI-People.pdf>

United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, *Guide: gender-inclusive communication*, 2022, retrieved from: https://www.unodc.org/documents/Gender/gender_sensitive_language/Gender-sensitiveCommsGuide-English-final.pdf

United Nations, *Transforming our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development*, 2015, retrieved from: <https://sdgs.un.org/sites/default/files/publications/21252030%20Agenda%20for%20Sustainable%20Development%20web.pdf>

Web Accessibility Initiative - WAI, *Easy Checks – A First Review of Web Accessibility*, 2023, retrieved from: <https://www.w3.org/WAI/test-evaluate/preliminary/#title>

